

IMMUNOHISTOCHEMICAL CHANGES IN THE LUNGS AFTER LOCAL AND GENERAL ANESTHESIA IN EXPERIMENTAL MECHANICAL TRAUMA

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Many authors have assessed the effective action of isoflurane using an ischemic pulmonary model with ex vivo reperfusion [13]. Based on these actions, researchers have concluded that when preliminary preconditioning with isoflurane occurs, vascular resistance indicators increase and pulmonary tissue edema. The authors performed a comparative assessment of sevoflurane and isoflurane in terms of their effect on reducing ischemic and reperfusion injury to lung tissue, and found that a single inhalation at a minimum alveolar concentration 30 minutes before ischemic reperfusion with any anesthetic resulted in a decrease in lung injury biomarkers in an ex vivo model [13–15].

The authors took into account existing studies on the effects of anesthetics on organs, primarily the heart, and proposed a number of hypothesis-based mechanisms of action, such as decreased secretion of tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF-alpha), decreased adhesion and migration of neutrophils, decreased levels of free oxygen radicals, and decreased metabolic rate [16]. Preconditioning with isoflurane resulted in a decrease in the level of lung tissue damage using lipopolysaccharide in the form of a sol; the study was conducted on mice [16, 17, 23]. This model of early preconditioning, administered 60 min before lung injury, is associated with a reduction in concentrated chemotactic chemokines, but the question remains whether this is a drug effect or a protective mechanism.

Another study showed that preconditioning with isoflurane or sevoflurane resulted in an increase in survival in sepsis-induced lung injury in rats [18, 23]. The protective mechanism remains unclear, despite the reduction in oxidation markers and the solubility of ICAM-1 levels with sevoflurane. The protective function provided by sevoflurane has been demonstrated in a pig autotransplanted lung model with reduced levels of TNF-alpha, interleukin-1 (IL-1), lipid peroxide, and nitric oxide (NO) [19, 21, 22].

Clinical studies report that preconditioning with sevoflurane reduces lung tissue edema and increases pulmonary vein PO₂ values with reimplantation of the lobes. It should be noted that oxygenation improved only briefly ten minutes after reimplantation, and returned to baseline values within half an hour.

Despite the short-term effect of sevoflurane during preconditioning, the results obtained are encouraging. The question of how this benefit for lung function can be translated into practical clinical practice is unclear [19–21]. The data obtained allow us to conclude that the issue of lung preconditioning during anesthesia remains open and unresolved. The experimental studies have demonstrated the protective mechanism during preconditioning, but it is difficult to apply these findings in clinical settings. To date, five clinical studies have been conducted on preconditioning of the patient's lungs during anesthesia [17–21], of which only one demonstrates an advantage in using remote ischemic preconditioning of the lung tissue [21]. Clinical studies devoted to the use of pharmacological drugs in this area are also currently lacking.

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